

1 **Lifr participates in germ layer lineage choice of pluripotent stem cells.**

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6 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
7 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
8 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
9 describe a requirement for the Lif receptor (Lifr) in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in
10 *Homo sapiens*.

11 Citations

12 1. Morgani, S.M. and Brickman, J.M., 2015. LIF supports primitive endoderm expansion during
13 pre-implantation development. *Development*, 142(20), pp.3488-3499.
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